

Formulation Development of Azelastine Hydrochloride In-Situ Ophthalmic Gel

Talat Farheen*, Anusha Suddala

Department of Pharmaceutics, Gokaraju Rangaraju College of pharmacy, Hyderabad

ABSTRACT

The present investigation concerns the development of a novel ocular drug delivery system utilizing the concept of in-situ gelation, which could remain on corneal surface and release the drug for longer period of time. Azelastine hydrochloride ocular in-situ gel was prepared using 32 factorial design, considering two variables; concentration of gellan gum and hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose K4M (HPMC K4M). The prepared factorial batches of ocular in-situ gels were subjected to evaluation for clarity, pH, drug content, gelling capacity, rheological studies, in-vitro drug release studies and stability studies. The drug content of various formulations was found in the range of 99.68 to 100.19% indicating the uniform distribution of drug. Formulations F4 and F5 showed more suitable gelling capacity, which completed the gelation immediately and formed stable gel for few hours, compared with the F6, F7, F8, and F9, which gelled instantaneously and were stable for extended period of time. These can also be reflected in the greater viscosity of F9, which would cause the formulation difficult to drop and gel difficult to spread out on cornea. The polymer concentration influenced the in-vitro drug release significantly in simulated tear fluid which suggested extended drug release from formulations. Regression analysis revealed that the drug release from the optimized batch followed zero order kinetics. From the above results, it was concluded that the ocular in-situ gels of Azelastine hydrochloride could be a viable alternative to conventional dosage forms because of the prolonged corneal residence time and sustained release of drug from the formulation.

Keywords: Azelastine hydrochloride, gellan gum, hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose K4M, ocular in-situ gels, extended release.

INTRODUCTION

The ocular drug delivery system is considered as a challenging system, as human eye is an important organ where the delivery of drug is quite difficult. The general process of drug absorption into the eye from the pre-corneal area (dose site) following topical ocular administration is quite complex. The sequence of events involves drug instillation, dilution in tear fluid, diffusion through mucin layer, corneal penetration (epithelium, stroma, endothelium), and transfer from cornea to aqueous humour. Following absorption, drug distributes to the site of action (e.g., iris-ciliary body). Parallel absorption via the conjunctiva/sclera provides an additional pathway to eye tissues but, for most drugs it is minor compared with corneal absorption. Also, non-productive, and parallel pathways (e.g., nasolacrimal drainage or systemic absorption via the conjunctiva) work to carry

drug away from the eye & limit the time allowed for the absorption process. Moreover, the conventional ocular formulations exhibit a poor bioavailability and short pre-corneal residence time due to rapid and extensive elimination of drugs from pre-corneal lachrymal fluid by lachrymation, solution drainage, and non-productive absorption by conjunctiva.

All these problems associated with conventional formulations can be overcome by developing *in-situ* gel. The term *in-situ* is derived from Latin which means, in its original place or in position.¹ *In-situ* gel forming systems are drug delivery systems that are in solution form before administration in the body but once administered, undergo gelation to form a gel triggered by external stimulus such as temperature, pH, ions etc. Both natural as well as synthetic polymers can be used for the formulation of *in-situ* gels.² The different approaches for *in-situ* gelling

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system are temperature induced *in-situ* gel systems, pH induced *in-situ* gel systems and ion activated systems. In ion triggered *in-situ* gelling system, solution viscosity increases upon exposure to ionic concentration of the tear fluids. It is also called osmotically induced gelation. Gelation increases the viscosity of formulation and the drug remain at the site for longer duration of time. Ion sensitive polymers are able to crosslink with cations (monovalent, divalent) present in lacrimal fluid on ocular surface and enhance the retention time of drug.² e.g: The polymer which shows osmotically induced gelation is Gelrite or Gellan gum, Hyaluronic acid and Alginates etc.³

Azelastine hydrochloride is a phthalazone derivative, its chemical name is (±)-1-(2H)-phthalazinone, 4[(4chlorophenyl) methyl]-2-(hexahydro-1-methyl-1Hazepin-4-yl)-, monohydrochloride. [Gill et al. (2018)]. It is a potent antiallergic compound with histamine H-receptor antagonist activity and a rapid onset (within 10 to 20 minutes) and long duration (up to 12 hours) of action. Azelastine has a triple mode of action: Antihistamine effect, Mast-cell stabilizing effect and anti-inflammatory effect.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Azelastine hydrochloride was obtained as a gift sample from Aurobindo pharma, Hyderabad. Gellan gum was obtained as a gift sample from marine hydrocolloids, Kerala. HPMC K4M, Mannitol, Di sodium EDTA, Benzalkonium chloride, Sodium hydroxide, Calcium chloride dihydrate, Sodium bicarbonate, sodium chloride obtained from Hi media limited, mumbai.

Pre-Formulation Studies

The quality and purity of the obtained drug was confirmed by its organoleptic properties, MP, solubility, Wavelength for maximum absorbance and FTIR. UV-VIS spectrophotometric method of analysis was validated for the procured drug. Statistical parameters like, precision, accuracy, LOD, LOQ were calculated. The compatibility of the procured drug and selected polymer was studied by UV-VIS spectro-photometry and Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy. Preliminary batches were prepared to optimize the concentrations of the selected polymers. The gelling capacity of these batches was determined by pouring a drop of the solution in a vial containing 2 ml of freshly prepared artificial tear fluid maintained at 37°C.

Preparation of Ocular *In-Situ* Gel

The factorial batches were formulated by design expert software using 3² factorial design. The design consists of selection of 2 independent variables at 3 levels (low, medium and high). The selected variables are: Gellan gum concentration(X1) and HPMC K4M concentration(X2). Weighed amounts of gellan gum and HPMC K4M were dispersed in double distilled water separately and stirred for 1h on magnetic stirrer and kept overnight for hydration. Next day both the polymer solutions were mixed together and drug was added with continuous stirring until it got dissolved. The mixture of mannitol and disodium EDTA solution in double distilled water was added with continuous stirring and pH was adjusted to 6. The prepared formulations were filtered and filled in the appropriate containers. The final containers were sterilized by autoclaving.^{4,5}

Table 1: Composition of ocular *in-situ* gels by using 3² factorial design

Formulation variables	Batch code								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Gellan gum (%)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.7
HPMC K4M (%)	0.25	0.5	0.75	0.25	0.5	0.75	0.25	0.5	0.75
Azelastine HCl (%)	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Di sodium EDTA (%)	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Mannitol (%)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Benzalkonium chloride (%)	0.00125	0.00125	0.00125	0.00125	0.00125	0.00125	0.00125	0.00125	0.00125

NaOH (ml)	q.s								
Distilled water (ml)	q.s								

Evaluation Of Factorial Batches

The clarity of the formulations before gelling was observed by visual inspection of the formulations against white and black backgrounds. The pH of the prepared *in-situ* gel formulations was measured using pH meter. Drug content was determined by taking 1ml of the formulation and diluting it to 100ml with distilled water. 1ml of diluted formulation was withdrawn and further diluted to 10 ml with distilled water. Concentration was determined at 214.2 nm by using UV visible spectroscopy. The gelling capacity was determined by pouring a drop of the solution in a vial containing 2 ml of freshly prepared artificial tear fluid maintained at 37°C. Gelation time and dissolution of formed gel was noted. Viscosity of the instilled formulation was used in determining the residence time of drug in the eye. Viscosity of formulation was determined before gelation by using the Brookfield's viscometer.⁶

Drug release was studied by using Franz diffusion cell and dialysis membrane.

- *In-vitro* release studies were carried out by using bi-chambered donor receiver compartment model (Franz diffusion cell).
- Receiver compartment was filled with artificial tear fluid (ATF).
- The dialysis membrane previously soaked overnight in simulated tear fluid, was sandwiched between the donor and receiver compartment.
- 1ml of the formulation was kept on a dialysis membrane in donor compartment and the medium in receptor compartment was stirred continuously to simulate blinking action.
- Aliquots of 3 ml were withdrawn at 1 hour time intervals up to 8 hours, equal volumes of fresh ATF were added to replace the withdrawn samples to maintain sink condition.
- Withdrawn samples were analyzed by UV spectrophotometer at 214.2 nm using ATF as blank.⁷

The release of drug from different dosage forms depends on the various factors like concentration, temperature, etc. There are several mathematical models for release kinetics which includes: Zero-order model, First order model, Higuchi Model, Hixson-Crowell model and Korsmeyer–Peppas model.⁵

A 3² full factorial design was selected and the 2 factors were evaluated at 3 levels. The Gellan gum concentration (X₁) and HPMC K4M concentration (X₂) were selected as independent variables and the dependent variables were percent drug release(Y1) and viscosity(Y2). The data obtained were treated using Stat-Ease Design Expert 11.1.1 software and analyzed statistically using analysis of variance (ANOVA). The 3D response surface curve was obtained to study the effect of X₁ and X₂ on dependent variables.

Ex-vivo corneal permeation studies: Goat cornea was used to examine the permeation. The cornea was carefully removed along with a 5-6 mm of surrounding scleral tissue and washed with cold saline. The washed corneas are kept in cold freshly prepared saline. Drug permeation study was done for the optimized formulation, by using Franz-diffusion cell in similar manner of *in-vitro* drug release except the membrane was replaced by cornea. The receptor compartment was filled with ATF and stirred on a magnetic stirrer.⁸

Ophthalmic preparations should be sterile therefore the test for sterility is very important evaluation parameter. The sterility test was performed as per the direct inoculation method reported in Indian Pharmacopoeia. 2 ml of the optimized formulation was taken out with a sterile syringe and needle. The test liquid was aseptically transferred to fluid thioglycolate medium (20 ml) and soybean-casein digest medium (20 ml) separately. The inoculated media was incubated for 14 days at 30°C to 35°C in the case of fluid thioglycolate medium and 20°C to 25°C in the case of soybean-casein digest media.⁹

The optimized formulation was placed in amber colored vials and sealed with aluminum foil for the short term accelerated study at 40°C±2°C and 75±5 %RH as per International Conference of Harmonization (ICH) Guidelines. After 3 months, the formulation was analyzed for gelling capacity, drug content, rheological evaluation and in-vitro drug release.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pre-formulation Studies

The melting point of the Azelastine hydrochloride was found to be 224.6°C, which is in good agreement with the literature value (225°C).¹⁰ Azelastine was found to be soluble in water and polyethylene glycol and slightly soluble in methanol, ethanol and octanol. The IR spectrum of procured drug azelastine hydrochloride was recorded and the presence of characteristic IR peaks confirmed the purity of drug. The wavelength of maximum absorbance was found to be 214.2nm. The standard graph of absorbance vs concentration of azelastine hydrochloride in ATF at 214.2nm was plotted. The calibration curve of azelastine hydrochloride exhibited a good correlation

between the concentrations and absorbance in the range 4-20 µg/ml ($r^2=0.9999$). Intraday and inter-day precisions were found to be 1.386 and 1.411 respectively. LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.95 and 2.986 respectively.

The UV spectroscopic method for compatibility study of drug and polymers showed that the drug and polymers are compatible with each other. The comparison of characteristic peaks in their IR spectrum of drug with the characteristic peaks in the IR spectrum of physical mixture of drug and gellan gum and drug and HPMC K4M suggested absence of any significant interaction between the selected drug and polymers.

From the observations of gelling capacity of preliminary batches, it was concluded that Gellan gum with 0.5%, 0.6%, and 0.7% and HPMC K4M with 0.25%, 0.5%, 0.75% were selected as they formed stable gels for a prolonged period of time. From the observations it was concluded that 1% of HPMC formed thick viscous solutions which are not suitable for instillation into eye. Gelling capacity of preliminary batches were mentioned in the table 2.

Table 2: Gelling capacity of preliminary batches

Preliminary batches	Gellan gum (%)	HPMC K4M (%)	Gelling capacity
PF1	0.5	0.75	+
PF2	0.6	0.5	++
PF3	0.7	0.25	+++
PF4	0.7	1	++++

+ - Gellation occurred in few minutes, remained for few hours

++ - Immediate gelation, remained for few hours

+++ - Immediate gelation, remained for extended period

++++ - Very stiff gel

Evaluation of Ocular *In-Situ* Gels

The drug content of the various factorial batches was found to be in the range of 99.68 to 100.19%. F1, F2 and F3 exhibited very weak gelation. F4 and F5 showed more suitable gelling capacity, which completed the gelation immediately and remained for few hours, compared with the F6, F7, F8, and F9, which gelled instantaneously and remained for extended period of time. This was also reflected as high viscosity of F9, which would cause the gel difficult to spread out on cornea and would make vision blurring.

Viscosity of the all formulations were observed at 20rpm and 30rpm and all the formulations showed the viscosity within the range. All the formulations have acceptable viscosities as the documented viscosity of *in-situ* gel systems should be (5-1000cps).¹¹

Table 3: Gelling capacity and viscosity of factorial batches

Factorial batch	Viscosity (cps)		Gelling capacity
	20 RPM	30 RPM	
F1	182	121.8	+
F2	227	228	+
F3	550	423	+

F4	240	386	++
F5	628	618	++
F6	681	618	++
F7	266	363.5	+++
F8	820	830	+++
F9	850	900	++++

+ - Gellation occurred in few minutes, remained for few hours
 ++ - Immediate gelation, remained for few hours
 +++ - Immediate gelation, remained for extended period
 ++++ - Very stiff gel

The *in-vitro* drug release for factorial batches F1-F9 for 8 hours suggested sustained drug release from formulations and was found to be in the range of 88.1 to 98.9% for 8 h of study. The F1-F3 formulations showed 98.9%, 96.8%, and 93.2% drug release over a period of 8 hrs. F4, F5, F6 showed 95.8%, 94.1%, and 91.3% drug release. 90.1% and 89.8% of the drug was released from F7 and F8. This additional sustained release effect was observed due to higher concentration of gellan gum and HPMC K4M. F9 showed least drug release (88.1%). 99.1% of drug was released in first 2h of study from pure drug as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: In-vitro percent drug release from procured drug (Azelastine hydrochloride) and factorial batches F1, F2, F3 and F4 in STF

Figure 2: In-vitro percent drug release of factorial batches in STF for F5, F6, F7, F8 and F9

From the observations of release profile, it was concluded that the developed formulations outperformed the pure drug by releasing the drug over a period of time and lead to prolonged therapeutic activity. Comparing all the factorial batches, F7

formulation sustained the drug release over a prolonged period of time with good gelling capacity and less viscous solution which can be administered easily into eye and is selected as an optimized formulation.

Table 4: Release kinetics data of optimized batch F7

Formulation	Kinetic models (R ²)				
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Hixon crowell	Peppas
F7	0.9879	0.8702	0.9379	0.725	0.6518

The drug release kinetic data indicated that the drug release from optimized batch F7 followed zero order kinetics (High R² value for zero order), suggesting sustained release of drug. In Korsmeyer-Peppas

model the n-value was found to be 1.2788 which corresponds to non-Fickian mechanism. Formulation followed Higuchi model for drug release suggesting drug release is diffusion controlled.^{12,13}

Figure 4: Higuchi model kinetics of in-vitro release of Azelastine HCl from the optimized batch

Statistical Evaluation of Data by Design Expert Software

ANOVA for Quadratic model

The model F-value for response 1 (Drug release), of 400.32 implies the model is significant. P-values less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant. In

this case A, B, AB, A², B² are significant model terms. Values greater than 0.1000 indicate the model terms are not significant. The model F-value for response 2 (Viscosity), of 20.66 implies the model is significant. P-values less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant. In this case A, B are significant model terms.¹⁴

Table 5: ANOVA for Drug release and viscosity

Drug release						
Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F-value	p-value	
Model	103.60	5	20.72	400.32	0.0002	Significant
A-Gellan gum	72.80	1	72.80	1406.54	< 0.0001	
B-HPMC K4M	24.81	1	24.81	479.27	0.0002	
AB	3.42	1	3.42	66.12	0.0039	
A ²	1.68	1	1.68	32.47	0.0107	
B ²	0.8889	1	0.8889	17.17	0.0255	
Residual	0.1553	3	0.0518			
Cor Total	103.76	8				
Viscosity						
Model	4.814E+05	2	2.407E+05	20.66	0.0020	Significant
A-Gellan gum	2.907E+05	1	2.907E+05	24.96	0.0025	
B-HPMC K4M	1.907E+05	1	1.907E+05	16.37	0.0068	
Residual	69891.52	6	11648.59			
Cor Total	5.513E+05	8				

Figure 5: Surface response curve for Response 1: Drug release

Figure 6: Surface response curve for Response 2: Viscosity

CONCLUSION

The present research work involves the formulation development of ocular *in-situ* gel of an anti-inflammatory agent, Azelastine hydrochloride. The factorial batches were prepared by using 3^2 factorial designs with the variable concentration of gellan gum, and HPMC K4M. The prepared factorial batches were evaluated for clarity, pH, drug content, gelling capacity, rheological study, *in-vitro* drug release studies and release kinetics.

The comparison of UV and IR spectra of pure drug with that of physical mixture of pure drug and polymers (gellan gum and HPMC K4M) suggested that there was no significant drug-excipients interaction. The preliminary batches were prepared to optimize the concentration of gellan gum and HPMC K4M. The batches with 0.5%, 0.6%, and 0.7% gellan gum and 0.25%, 0.5%, and 0.75% HPMC K4M concentrations resulted in formation of nearly clear ocular gels, which was then selected for the formulation of factorial batches. Factorial batches were formulated based on 3^2 factorial designs, where the selected independent variables were concentration of gellan gum and concentration of HPMC K4M. The effect of independent parameters on dependent parameters i.e drug release and viscosity were studied. The drug content of various formulations was found to be in the range of 99.68 to 100.19% indicating the uniform distribution of drug. Gelling capacity of the factorial batches F1, F2, F3 exhibited weak gelation, F4 and F5 showed more suitable gelling capacity, which completed the gelation immediately and remained for few hours, compared with the F6, F7, F8, and F9, which gelled instantaneously and remained for extended period of time. The polymer concentration influenced the *in-vitro* drug release significantly in simulated tear fluid which suggested sustained drug release from formulations and was found to be in the range of 88.1 to 98.9%. The *in-vitro* drug release study for pure drug showed complete drug release within 2 hours, whereas the factorial batches sustained the drug release up to 8 hours. Ocular *in-situ* gels obtained with higher polymer concentration resulted in sustained drug release, which means higher the concentration of HPMC and gellan gum, lesser the drug release from the formulations.

Based on the observations, the batch F7 showed good results with clarity, pH, gelling capacity, viscosity, release kinetics, and *in-vitro* drug release sustained up to 8 h, Hence it was considered as an optimized batch. The optimized batch showed a zero order release kinetics suggesting the sustained drug release from the formulation F7 and Higuchi model indicating drug release is diffusion controlled. Based on the above discussion, it can be concluded that the ocular *in-situ* gels of Azelastine hydrochloride can be successfully developed by using 3^2 factorial designs in order to obtain sustain drug release, to increase the precorneal residence time, reduce dosing frequency of conventional dosage form and to improve patient compliance.

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